

AN ASSESSMENT OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS AND ITS DETERMINANTS AMONG STUDENTS OF EDO STATE COLLEGE OF NURSING SCIENCES, BENIN CITY, EDO STATE, NIGERIA.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16841318>

Abstract

Academic performance is measured either by continuous assessment or cumulative grade point average. Students who have good academic achievements had higher income, better employment benefits, and more advancement opportunities. This study assessed the academic performance of students and its determinants among students of Edo State College of Nursing Sciences Benin city, Edo State, Nigeria. A descriptive cross-sectional study design was used for this study. A convenient sampling method was used to select 105 study participants. Data was collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Results shows that majority of the students [93(89%)] had good academic performance while less than half [11(11%)] had poor academic performance. Good academic performance was reported in students who studied for more than five hours [17 (16.3%)], studied ([45 (43.3%)]); [48(46.1%)], less than 4hours [40(38.5%)] daily had good academic performance. More than half of the respondents [73(78.5%)] who had interest in studying had Good academic performance compared to twenty students (21.5%) who showed poor academic performance. Interest in studying was statistically significant ($p=0.017$) with academic performance. Program ($p=0.519$), marital status ($p=0.895$), and average monthly income ($p=0.594$) did not show association with academic performance. In conclusion, the importance of investment by governments in schools cannot be overemphasized.

Keywords: Academic, Performance, students

Introduction

Higher education institutions play a pivotal role in producing qualified human power that can solve community problems (Idris, 2012). At the micro-level, it is associated with better living standards for individuals through improved productivity; given that those who have received a higher education tend to have more economic and social opportunities. At the macro level, education builds well-informed and skilled human capital, which has been considered an engine of economic growth, that positively contributes to economic development (Sothan, 2019). However, gaining knowledge, attitudes, values, and skills through education is not a simple task; rather it is a long and challenging trip in life. Students are expected to spend much of their time studying and need to graduate with good academic results.

Nursing education is challenging and expensive all over the world resulting in nursing colleges aiming to recruit only the best applicants into its programs. Despite going for the best brain, these students on getting into the school struggle to cope with the rigorous nature of the training. Most of them are from families with low socioeconomic status and are faced with herculean task of surviving the economic hardship and rigorous school work.

Academic performance is the extent to which a student, teacher, or institution has attained their short or long-term educational goals and is measured either by continuous assessment or cumulative grade point average (CGPA) (Talib 2012). A correlational study among vocational high school students in Indonesia found that students who had good academic achievements have higher income, better employment benefits, and more advancement opportunities (Tentama, 2019}. Besides, academically successful students have higher self-esteem and self-confidence, low levels of anxiety and depression, are socially inclined, and are less likely to engage in substance abuse, i.e., alcohol and khat (Regier, 2011).

Poor academic performance among students is on the rise due to a lot of distractions. However, a cross-sectional study in Malaysia in higher learning institutions reported that an increasing number of students still do not graduate on time, suggesting that they did not perform well in their studies (Abrazak, 2019). Despite excessive government investment in education, most students fail to achieve good academic performance at all levels of education. A correlational study in Arba Minch University, South Ethiopia, reported that the trend of graduating students is not proportional to the trend of enrolled students and more students commit readmission due to poor academic performance (Yigermal, 2017). This resulted in unemployment, poverty, drugs elicit, promiscuity, homelessness, illegal activities, social isolation, insufficient health insurance, and dependence. Additionally, a systematic review in India concluded that poor academic achievement causes significant stress to the parents and low self-esteem to the students [Karande, 2005]. It is also significantly associated with high anxiety scores among university students in Pakistan [Talib 2012]. Further, in public schools in Pakistan, academic failure affects self-concept and leads to a feeling of disturbance and shock. In this way, students finally drop out of the education system at all (Chohan, 2018).

Beyond the quality of schools, various personal and family factors, including socioeconomic factors, english ability, class attendance, employment, high school grades, and academic self-efficacy have been proposed to influence academic performance. Besides, other factors, i.e., teaching skills, study hours, family size, and parental involvement have an association with academic performance as well (Crede and Mushtaq 2012). A cohort study among university students in Australia concluded that aging does not impede academic achievement (Imlach 2017). A secondary data analysis among fifth-grade students in Colorado showed that eating breakfast, normal body mass index, adequate sleep, and ≥ 5 days' physical

activity per week was significantly associated with higher cumulative grades (Stroebele, 2013). A significant association was also found between joining the medical profession and good academic performance in Pakistan (Khan 2020). At Arba Minch University, students with a good academic record before campus entry were more likely to have academic success in higher education programs (Yigermal, 2017) A descriptive study on Bahir Dar university students showed that the education status of parents and attending night club affect academic performance (Tirumeh, 2014). Also, a survey in Nigerian high schools indicated students whose parents were government employees achieved better performance (Atolagbe, 2019). However, the impact of these factors varies from region to region and differs in cities and rural areas. This might be due to diverse data measurement methods and quality or the context of each study.

The poor performance of students requests attention. There is however paucity of researches on this subject in south-south Nigeria, It is hoped that understanding predictors of good academic performances among nursing students will not only add to the existing body of knowledge on this subject but also assist in the development of programs that will address these issues to improve academic performance among students.

This study assessed the determinants of academic performance among students of Edo State College of Nursing Sciences Benin city Edo State Nigeria.

Methodology

A descriptive cross-sectional study design was used for this study. All students who undergo their education in the Nursing and Midwifery and are available at the time of data collection were included in the study. Students who had not written a semester exam, mentally and physically incompetent, and those who were not willing to fill out the questionnaire were excluded. A convenient sampling technique was used to select 105 study participants. Data was collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire and academic performance among student's who scored a cumulative GPA of 2.8 and above were categorized as "Good", whereas those with a cumulative GPA of below 2.75 were categorized as "Poor" (Yigermal, 2017). Data was analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Univariate analysis was done. The Chi-square analysis was used to assess initial associations between the independent and outcome variables. Chi-square analysis was used to test association between independent variables and academic performances in surveyed students. P was set at $P \leq 0.05$. Ethical clearance for this study was gotten from the ethics and research committee of the ministry of health and permission was sought from the management of the institution.

Results of the Study

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Characteristics	Frequency (n=105)	Percent
Program		
Nursing	62	59.6
Midwifery	42	40.4
Cohort		
Nursing cohort 1	6	5.8
Midwifery cohort 1	24	23.0
Nursing cohort 2	20	19.2
Nursing cohort 3	33	31.7
Midwifery cohort 2	17	16.3
Mean Age		
20.15 ± 7.533		
Sex		
Male	15	14.4
Female	88	84.6
Family visits		
Weekly	30	28.8
Bimonthly	10	9.6
Monthly	24	23.1
Nil	38	36.5
Dependents		
Yes	62	59
No	42	40

Family Size

<3

>3 15 14.4

67 83.7

Monthly allowance

<10,000 52 49.5

10,000-20000 18 17.1

21000-30000 25 23.9

>30000 28 26

Others

Mean Age **20.15 ± 7.533**

Fig 1: Academic Performance

Table 2: Relationship between academic performance and examination preparation

Variables	Academic Performance		p-value
	Poor	Good	
How many hours do you study			
<3hrs	7 (6.7)	45 (43.3)	0.592 ⁺
>5hrs	1 (1)	17 (16.3)	
4-5hrs	3 (2.9)	31 (30)	
Sleeping hours per day			
< 4hrs	5 (4.8)	40 (38.5)	0.061 ⁺
5-6 hours	3 (2.9)	48 (46.1)	
7hrs & above	3 (2.9)	5(4.8)	
Library time (n=89)			
Poor	7 (6.7)	50 (48.1)	0.365 ⁺
Good	2(2)	30 (29)	
Exam preparation			
<1 month	7 (6.7)	29 (28)	0.249 ⁺
>1 month	4 (3.8)	64 (61.5)	
Interest in studying			
No	6 (54.5)	5(45.5)	0.017 ⁺
Yes	20 (21.5)	73 (78.5)	
Mode of studying for exams			
Discussion with friends	3 (2.9)	25(24)	0.507
Practice past question	0 (0.0)	3 (2.9)	
Reading lecture materials	1(1)	28(26.9)	
Reading lecture notes & textbook	4(3.8)	15(14.4)	
Study alone	3(2.9)	22(22)	

⁺Chi-square test

Table 3: Relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and academic performance.

Variables	Academic Performance		p-value
	Poor	Good	

Program			
Midwifery	3 (7.1)	39 (92.9)	0.519 ⁺
Nursing	8 (12.9)	54 (87.1)	
Marital status			
< Married	1 ()	7 ()	0.895 ⁺
Single	10 ()	86 ()	
Average monthly income			
<10,000	5 (6.7)	47 ()	0.594 ⁺
10,000-20,000	2 (2)	16 ()	
21,000-30,000	0	9	
>31,000	4	21	

⁺*Chi-square test*

The mean age of the students was 20.15 ± 7.533 . More than half of the respondents [62 (59.6%)] are nursing students, with Nursing cohort 1 having the least response [6(5.8%)] due to attrition. A greater proportion of students [38(36.5%)] do not go home till end of the semester. Majority of the respondents are females [88 (84.6%) while less than half of the students [15 (14.4%) are males.

Majority of the students [93(89%)] had good academic performance while less than half [11(11%)] had poor academic performance

Moreso, students who studied for more than five hours [17 (16.3%)] had good academic performance. While those [45 (43.3%)] who studied for less than three hours daily also had good academic performance. One third of the students who slept for 5-6 hours [48(46.1%)], less than 4hours [40(38.5%)] daily had good academic performance. This did not show any significance with academic performance of students ($p=0.061$).

Off the students who utilized the library, more than half of them [50(48.1%)] who poorly utilized the library had good academic performance while on thirty students (29%) had good utilization of the library and academic performance. Students [64(61.5%)] who used more than one month to prepare for examination had good academic performance compared to twenty-nine (28%) who prepared for exam less than a month. How this did not show any statistical association ($p=0.249$) with academic performance. More than half of the respondents [73(78.5%)] who had interest in studying had Good academic performance compared to twenty students (21.5%) who showed poor academic performance. Interest in studying was statistically significant ($p=0.017$) with academic performance. Program ($p=0.519$), marital status ($p=0.895$), and average monthly income ($p=0.594$) did not show association with academic performance.

Discussion

Majority of the students had good academic performance while less than half had poor academic performance. This is similar to a study in Ethiopia that reported good academic performance among students (Tadese, 2022). Internet is beneficial to students; it enhances their capabilities and skills during their studies. Moreso, the good academic performance reported is due to the robust educational resources and internet available to student's which students access for research purposes, assignments, and presentations. Similarly, Emeka and Nyeche (2016) argue that the Internet is beneficial for students, which enhances their capabilities and skills which are helpful in their studies. Not having students exposed to other learning sources will lead to poor academic performance which will lead to prolonged stay in school [Abrazak, 2019; Yigermal, 2017]. Poor academic performance will lead to student drop out from school (Chohan, 2018).

This study found that students who studied, sleep less, spent time in the library and prepare early for exams had good academic performance. Crede and Mushtaq (2012) reported that study hours improve

academic performance of students. Moreso, the quest to improve students' current and future life stimulate students to do better academically (Kell et al., 2013).

This study found that, students who had interest in studying had good academic performance. Interest in studying showed association with academic performance. The clinical nature of the profession encourages students to study. This similar to findings in a previous study that found academic performance associated with faculty (Tadese, 2022). learning ability is one of the factors that influenced students' academic performance in higher education. Learning ability is where students are capable of doing their best in their studies including motivating themselves in achieving what they want in their studies and life (Sivrikaya, 2019).

Factors that play a role in satisfaction are the student's interest in the subject and their eagerness to understand it. Their attitude toward learning activities is affected by their personal characteristics, and this is especially true for group activities (Lee 2008). Program, marital status, monthly income did not show any association with academic performance. This is different from a study that found that students who visit their families on a weekly basis were more likely to have better academic performances than those in corresponding categories (Ekwochi U, 2019). Also a study in Indonesia found that students who had good academic achievements have higher income, better employment benefits, and more advancement opportunities [Tentama, 2019]. In conclusion, good academic performance can help students attain their desire future goals. It is important that nursing students study hard to attain it and prevent dropping out from school and prolong stay in the institution.

Limitation of the study

This study is limited by our criteria for assessing academic performance in surveyed students which was based on the feedback from the nursing students which was not verified by viewing official results. This may have been a potential source of bias due to the possibility of unwillingness of some respondents to admit their real results.

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